

Comparison of GCC and PCC as Coating Material in Paper Production

Ahmet TUTUŞ¹, Mustafa ÇİÇEKLER^{1*}, Ufuk KILLI², Muharrem KAPLAN²

¹Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Faculty of Forestry, Forest Industry Eng. Dep., Kahramanmaraş/ Turkey
²ADACAL Industrial Minerals I.C., Afyon/Turkey

* **Corresponding Author:** mcicekler87@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of the coating process is to improve whiteness, brightness, opacity, surface smoothness and water resistance of paper and board. In this study, the effects of PCC and GCC on the physical and optical properties of coated papers were investigated. Writing and printing papers were produced with using bleached short (70%) and long (30%) fiber mixtures. Calcium carbonate (86.7%), starch (15%) and carboxymethyl cellulose (0.3) were used as coating materials. Precipitated (PCC) and ground (GCC) calcium carbonates were adjusted to 50% concentration with tap water. Coating suspensions were prepared with PCC and GCC mixtures and applied to paper surfaces with coating rod (no:2). The coated papers were dried at room condition and calendered under 15 bar pressure at 100°C. The physical and optical properties of the coated papers were investigated and compared with each other. The results show that using PCC as coating material increased the optical properties of the papers and gave better results than GCC. The breaking length was found to be higher with using GCC. In terms of surface roughness, there were differences between of GCC and PCC coated papers. As a result, the use of PCC instead of GCC as a coating material has been found to improve the optical properties and the surface roughness of paper. The improvement of optical properties is costly for papermakers and this problem can be solved with using PCC as a coating materials.

Keywords: Coating, GCC, PCC, paper.

1. Introduction

After beating vegetable fibers with special tools, felting and fringing of fibers and swelling by water, the formation of hydrogen bonds by drying the sheet formed on the sieve has a definite endurance and this structure is called as paper (Eroglu ve Usta, 2004).

Writing-printing papers have 60-80 grammages and are suitable for writing and printing. The structure of the paper consists of chemical cellulose or chemical cellulose and mechanical wood pulps mixture. Coating is also applied to paper based on its usage area (Yakut, 2012).

Two methods are commonly used to improve the print quality of paper. The first is that the paper is passed through the super calender after 18 to 25% of the filler is added to the fiber suspension during the paper production. With this method, filling materials with small diameters can improve the quality of paper by improving the surface quality (Eroglu and Usta, 2004; Bucak, 2014). The second method is to give a regular structure to the surface after the production of the paper. This method is to regulate the irregularities in the surface of the paper layer by plastering just as the wall plaster does. The process of covering the surface of the paper with a plaster consisting of mineral substances and adhesives is called paper plastering or coating (Eroglu and Usta, 2004; Bucak, 2014).

It is desired that an ideal filler material should have a high whiteness, an appropriate refractive index and particle distribution, a high retention in the paper, a low density, no show chemically reactive properties, low abrasiveness and low cost (Erkan and Malayoglu, 2001). Calcium carbonate is a pigment that is very much involved in the paper industry after kaolin. It is used as filler in the paper and as a coating material on the paper surface. The particle size is usually 2-3 microns, but it can range from 7-8 microns depending on the carbonate species. The whiteness of calcium carbonates is in the range of 93-98 and is easily dispersed in water (Ozden, 1998).

Ground calcium carbonate (GCC) is obtained by grinding natural limestone with water and subjecting it to air or water separation to obtain a product of the desired particle size (Ozden, 1998). As the precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) can be crystallized in the desired morphological properties, it can change both the chemical and physical properties of the paper when it is used as a coating mineral and as a filler. PCC is used in dyeing and toothpaste production, in paper industry as filler and coating material and in rubber making as filler (Eroglu and Usta, 2004; Bucak, 2014).

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of GCC and PCC which are used both as filler pigment and as coating material in the paper industry on the physical and optical properties of the papers coated with these minerals.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Material

PCC was taken from Adacal Industrial Minerals I.C. GCC, CMC, starch and short and long fibers were supplied from the market. This study was carried out by Adacal Industrial Minerals I.C. and Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Department of Forest Industry Engineering collaboration.

2.2. Paper Production and Coating Process

PCC and GCC used as pigment in coating process. PCC, GCC, and starch were prepared as separate suspensions at specific concentrations for coating process. The prepared suspensions were mixed to a homogeneous state in a beaker based on the ratios given in Table 1. PCC and GCC ratios were changed and 12 different coating experiments shown in same table were performed.

Table 1. Coating suspension recipes

	Pigment (%)	PCC (%)	GCC (%)	Starch (%)	CMC (%)
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	84.7	100	0	15	0.3
3	84.7	0	100	15	0.3
4	84.7	10	90	15	0.3
5	84.7	20	80	15	0.3
6	84.7	30	70	15	0.3
7	84.7	40	60	15	0.3
8	84.7	50	50	15	0.3
9	84.7	60	40	15	0.3
10	84.7	70	30	15	0.3
11	84.7	80	20	15	0.3
12	84.7	90	10	15	0.3

The bleached short (70%) and long (30%) fibers were beaten in the hollander beater to 45 ± 5 °SR (Schopper Riegler) freeness levels according to Tappi T 200 sp-96 and ten handsheets

per tested sequence with grammages of 80 gr.m^{-2} were prepared using a Rapid-Kothen sheet former according to ISO 5269/2.

The prepared coating suspensions were applied to the paper surfaces by coating rod (no.2) three times. The coated papers were conditioned at $23 \pm 1 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 1\%$ relative humidity in a conditioning room and then subjected to calendering at $100 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 15 bar pressures.

2.3. Determination of the physical and optical properties

Coated papers kept in the conditioning room for 24 hours were subjected to physical and optical properties in accordance with the standards given in Table 2 below.

Table 2. The physical and optical tests applied to coated paper

Physical and Optical Tests	Standards
Breaking length	TAPPI T494 om-01
Burst index	TAPPI T403 om-15
Surface Roughness	ISO 4287
Bulkiness	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Density	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Brightness	ISO 2469:2014
Whiteness	ISO 2469:2014
Yellowness	ASTM E313
Opacity	TAPPI T519 om-02

Three replicates were done for each experiment, and mean values were used to determine the physical and optical properties of the coated papers.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of PCC and GCC Ratios on the Physical Properties

Table 3 shows test results of the physical properties of the coated paper such as breaking length, burst index, surface roughness, bulkiness and density depending on PCC and GCC ratios. The results indicated that the breaking lengths and burst indices have been significantly reduced with coating process (Fig. 1).

Table 3. The physical properties of the coated papers

	PCC (%)	GCC (%)	Breaking length (km)	Burst index (kPa.m ² /g)	Surface Roughness (ml/min)	Bulkiness (cm ³ /g)	Density (g/cm ³)
1	0	0	5.83	4.06	327	1.43	0.70
2	100	0	5.55	3.85	290	1.55	0.65
3	0	100	5.68	3.90	326	1.54	0.65
4	10	90	5.25	3.78	323	1.58	0.64
5	20	80	5.25	3.68	317	1.56	0.64
6	30	70	5.19	3.50	311	1.57	0.64
7	40	60	5.81	3.56	308	1.55	0.65
8	50	50	5.49	4.03	304	1.56	0.64
9	60	40	5.68	3.90	302	1.56	0.64
10	70	30	5.55	3.83	300	1.54	0.65
11	80	20	5.34	4.03	297	1.54	0.65
12	90	10	5.37	3.87	295	1.53	0.65

When compared with non-coated writing-printing papers, the breaking length values were decreased about 4.80%, 2.57%, 9.94%, 9.94%, 10.97%, 0.34%, 5.83%, 2.57%, 4.80%, 8.40% and 7.89% and burst indices were also decreased about 5.17%, 3.94%, 6.89%, 9.35%, 13.79%, 12.31%, 0.73%, 3.94%, 5.66%, 0.73% and 4.67%, respectively. However, there are no significant effects on the bulkiness, density and surface roughness values.

Figure 1. Physical properties of coated papers

In a study, the physical and optical properties of the paper were examined by adding PCC and GCC as fillers at certain ratios to the paper. They reported that PCC and GCC had a negative effect on the physical properties of the papers (Tutus et al., 2012).

In another study, PCC and GCC had used in newspaper, wrapping paper and writing-printing paper production as filler and the fillers were compared with each other in terms of

effects on the paper properties. According to results of this study, fillers reduced the physical properties of the papers. Because PCC has regular grain size, grain shape and size distribution, it had given the better results than GCC (Tutus et al., 2013).

3.2. The Effects of PCC and GCC Ratios on Optical Properties

Table 4 shows test results of the optical properties of the coated paper such as whiteness, brightness, yellowness and opacity depending on PCC and GCC ratios.

Table 4. The optical properties of the coated papers

	PCC (%)	GCC (%)	Whiteness (ISO)	Brightness (ISO)	Yellowness (E313)	Opacity (ISO)
1	0	0	76.69	74.71	3.31	92.89
2	100	0	82.99	81.67	1.99	96.29
3	0	100	82.07	80.59	2.29	95.92
4	10	90	81.71	80.14	2.44	95.72
5	20	80	81.61	80.13	2.30	95.63
6	30	70	81.47	80.00	2.27	95.97
7	40	60	82.05	80.59	2.23	95.93
8	50	50	82.33	80.95	2.13	95.91
9	60	40	83.00	81.17	1.79	96.24
10	70	30	83.63	81.26	2.08	96.09
11	80	20	83.99	81.73	1.90	96.33
12	90	10	84.14	81.86	1.93	96.40

There were significant increases in the optical properties such as whiteness, brightness and opacity with coating process (Fig. 2). The main reason for these increases is the high optical properties of PCC and GCC. Besides, the papers surface properties had been improved by coating process. When compared with non-coated writing-printing papers, the whiteness values were increased about 8.21%, 7.01%, 6.54%, 6.41%, 6.23%, 6.98%, 7.35%, 8.22%, 9.05%, 9.52% and 9.71% and brightness values were also increased about 9.31%, 7.87%, 7.26%, 7.25%, 7.08%, 7.87%, 8.35%, 9.50%, 8.76%, 9.39% and 11.28%, respectively.

When compared with non-coated papers, PCC and GCC has been improved the yellowness and opacity values of the writing-printing papers. However, there is no significant differences between opacity and yellowness values when PCC and GCC compared with each other.

Figure 2. Optical properties of the coated papers.

Tutus et al., (2013) investigated that the effects of PCC and GCC as filler on the optical and physical properties of papers produced by recycling newspaper, packing and writing-printing papers. It was found that fillers reduced the physical properties of papers but improved optical properties such as whiteness and brightness values.

In another study, the physical and optical properties of the paper were examined by adding PCC and GCC as fillers at different ratios to the paper. It has been reported that compared to kaolin, GCC and other fillers, PCC provides better whiteness and brightness values due to its whiter and brighter structure (Tutus et al., 2012).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The prerequisite for print quality is that the paper surface has a homogeneous smoothness and whiteness. The coating process is needed for providing ideal printing surface. Since the ink contacts the coated layer during printing, the printability of this surface must have optimum values. Therefore, coating process is one of the most important steps of the paper industry. As a result of this study;

1. It has been determined that with using adacal PCC as coating mineral, paper surface has a more homogeneous structure and optical properties of the papers such as whiteness, brightness, yellowness and opacity have been improved.
2. It was observed that the physical properties of the papers were decreased with using PCC in coating process but these decreases were insignificant.

3. Improvements were observed in surface roughness of papers while the whiteness values which is the most important parameter for print quality has been increased with using PCC in coating process.
4. It has been also observed that using adacal PCC in coating process has better effects on the physical and optical properties of the writing-printing papers than GCC.

References

- Eroglu, H. and Usta, M., (2004). *Paper and Cardboard Production Technology*, Volume I, Cellulose and Paper Industry Foundation, Trabzon.
- Yakut, A., (2012). Review of New Paper Production from Recyclable Used Paper. *Installation Engineering* - Issue 127 - January / February
- Erkan, Z.E., and Malayođlu, U., (2001, October). Industrial Raw Materials and Their Properties Used in Paper-Cardboard Industry. *4 Industrial Raw Materials Symposium* (pp.250-257). Izmir: Dokuz Eylöl University
- Ozden, O., (1998). *Use of Starch for Coating the Paper Surface*. Doctoral Thesis. Istanbul University, Institute of Science and Technology, Istanbul.
- Bucak, F., (2014). *Evaluation of Textile Residues on Paper Blank*. Master Thesis. Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University, Institute of Science and Technology, Kahramanmaraş
- Tutus, A., Cicekler, M., Kazaskeroglu, Y., Muduroglu, M., (2012). Effects of Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC) on Optical and Physical Properties of Paper. *8th International Minerals Symposium*. pp.147-152. İstanbul/Turkey
- Tutus, A., Cicekler, M., Ozdemir, A., Okan, O,T., (2013). Effects of Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC) on Optical Properties of Waste Paper, *International Caucasian Forestry Symposium*. pp.884-887. Artvin/Turkey.